

Supplementary Online Material

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1- EPSAPG Evaluation on TMSEG

1.1- Segment Prediction Analysis

TMSEG segment-based predictions represent the predicted regions (a segment of consecutive residues) of a query sequence where those segments match the transmembrane helix regions of the ground truth. That being said, for each sequence (also referred to as instance in this SOM) we can compute the recall of correctly predicted segments/regions in a protein sequence.

Figure S1. Segment-based TMSEG prediction analysis to the ground truth. (a) represents the recall distribution, which is the percentage distribution of how many segments in a sequence ground truth are correctly predicted using EPSAPG profiles. (b) represents the recall distribution, which is the percentage distribution of how many segments in a sequence ground truth are correctly predicted using PSI-BLAST profiles.

The histogram distributions of the recall (Figure S1) show that we have roughly a similar number of correctly predicted segments from both tools. Also, half of the instances (Figure S1-a&b), segments in a particular sequence, are 100% correctly predicted. Furthermore, from a statistical point of view and comparing the overall similarity means, EPSAPG has a recall mean of **0.607** with a standard deviation of **0.430**. Whereas PSI-BLAST has a recall mean of **0.621** with a standard deviation of **0.416**. We observe that both tools have again roughly a similar performance. Furthermore, I checked whether the ratio of correctly predicted regions on the same sequence is similar using either PSI-BLAST or EPSAPG. To perform that, I calculated the absolute difference of the recall between EPSAPG and PSI-BLAST generated predictions on the same protein sequence as shown in Figure S2. The analysis demonstrates that more than 80% of the recall of predicted pairs are the same with an absolute difference mean of **0.0005** and a standard deviation of **0.281**.

Figure S2. TMSEG PSSM-based predictions recall absolute differences on similar amino acid sequences. The difference is computed based on the recall of correctly predicted regions of the same protein sequence using PSI-BLAST and EPSAPG profiles.

1.2 - Large Dataset Analysis

To make sure that the sample was representative, I checked whether the statistics computed previously still generalize for the whole TMSEG dataset, of about 8817 protein sequences. Since running PSI-BLAST on this dataset was no affordable the evaluation was done using EPSAPG only.

Table S1. EPSAPG runtime of running the whole TMSEG dataset against a random sample of 68 million proteins from uniref90. As sequences are processed sequentially in PSI-BLAST, an extrapolation by the average runtime per sequence of 11min would lead to about 1 month and half required time. On the other hand, EPSAPG took only 2h50m to generate PSSM profiles.

Number of seqs	EPSAPG runtime
8817	170m 11s / 2h 50m

The runtime needed to get the PSSM files via EPSAPG is considerably fast (Table S1). We see that EPSAPG needs only 170 minutes to generate the PSSMs while PSI-BLAST would take a month and a half. We observe here a significant decrease in runtime by almost 540 folds.

Figure S3. Analysis of EPSAPG profile-based predictions on the whole TMSEG dataset. (a) represents the recall distribution, which is the percentage distribution of how many segments in a sequence ground truth are correctly predicted. (b) represents the percentage distribution of how similar the residue-level predictions in a sequence are to the ground truth labels.

The large dataset analysis (Figure S3) demonstrates that the distributions of both recall and character-wise similarity percentages are preserved. From a statistical standpoint, EPSAPG has a recall mean of **0.676** with a standard deviation of **0.357**, which is a little bit higher than the smaller sample results.

Likewise, EPSAPG has a similarity mean of **0.863** with a standard deviation of **0.093**, which is again a bit higher than the small sample statistic. The analysis is summarized in Table S2.

For statistical significance, the standard error was calculated using the following formula:

$$StdErr = \frac{StdDev}{\sqrt{Number\ of\ Samples}}$$

Table S2. TMSEG statistical significance comparison of the segment-based recall and the character-wise similarity percentage analysis. Overall, from a statistical significance perspective, EPSAPG performance is better than PSI-BLAST.

	TMSEG Large Dataset Statistics (Figure S3) – using EPSAPG	TMSEG Sample Dataset Statistics (Figure 4.a & S1-a) – using EPSAPG	TMSEG Sample Dataset Statistics (Figure 4-b & S1-b) – using PSI-BLAST
Character-wise similarity percentage	86.3% ± 0.01	83.0% ± 0.77	83.2% ± 0.73
Segment-Based recall	67.6% ± 0.38	60.7% ± 2.64	62.1% ± 2.55

2- EPSAPG Evaluation on REPROF

2.1 - Large Dataset Analysis

Similarly to TMSEG, I wanted to make sure that the sample I tested on is representative. I wanted to check whether the statistics computed previously still hold for the whole REPROF dataset of 4692 protein sequences. Since running PSI-BLAST on this dataset is not affordable, an estimated three weeks is required, the evaluation was conducted using EPSAPG only.

Table S3. EPSAPG required runtime to run the whole REPROF dataset against a random sample of 68 million proteins from uniref90. As sequences are processed sequentially in PSI-BLAST, an extrapolation by the average runtime of 11min would lead to about 3 weeks. On the other hand, EPSAPG took only 73 min to generate PSSM profiles.

Number of seqs	EPSAPG runtime
4692	73m 24s

The runtime needed to get the PSSM files is again faster. EPSAPG needs only 73m 24s (Table S3) to generate the PSSMs while PSI-BLAST would take about three weeks. A significant improvement of runtime by almost 414 folds is achieved.

Figure S4. Analysis of PSSM-based predictions of the large REPROF dataset. The histogram represents the percentage distribution of how similar the secondary structure residue predictions in a sequence to the ground truth labels resulting from EPSAPG PSSM profiles

The large dataset analysis (Figure S4) demonstrates that the distribution of the character-wise similarity percentage is preserved. The histogram depicts a roughly sharp Gaussian distribution of the predictions, with a mean around 0.8. From a statistical point of view, computing the overall similarity mean and comparing it to the previously evaluated sample, EPSAPG has a similarity mean of **0.783** with a standard deviation of **0.102**, which is comparable to the small sample statistics.

The analysis is summarized in Table S4.

Table S4. REPROF statistical significance comparison of the character-wise similarity percentage. Statistical significance of the three tests confirms that EPSAPG performs generally the same as PSI-BLAST.

	REPROF Large Dataset Statistics (Figure S4) – using EPSAPG	REPROF Sample Dataset Statistics (Figure 6-a) – using EPSAPG	REPROF Sample Dataset Statistics (Figure 6-b) – using PSI-BLAST
Character-wise similarity percentage	78.3% ± 0.15	78.1% ± 0.58	77.9% ± 0.58

3- EPSAPG Evaluation on LocTree2

Figure S5. LocTree2 confusion matrix predictions of 177 proteins selected at random from the different classes of the DeepLoc dataset. The selection was done randomly at the class level, but in a balanced way with regard to the classes distribution. The experiment was done only on eukaryotic organisms as being the one with most classes. The experiment was conducted on PSSMs generated with PSI-BLAST.

Figure S6. LocTree2 confusion matrix predictions of 177 proteins selected at random from the different classes of the DeepLoc dataset. The selection was done randomly at the class level, but in a balanced way with regard to the set class distribution. The experiment was done only on eukaryotic organisms as being the one with most classes. The experiment was conducted on PSSMs generated with EPSAPG.

Figure S7. LocTree2 confusion matrix predictions of 600 proteins selected at random from the different classes of the DeepLoc dataset. The experiment was conducted only on eukaryotic organisms as being the one with most classes. The experiment was conducted on PSSMs generated with EPSAPG.